

***India is an Incredible Place for Education:
A Cursory Glance***

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INDIA IS AN INCREDIBLE PLACE FOR EDUCATION: A CURSORY GLANCE

1.0 PROLOGUE

India, from ancient times, has been a center of higher learning as it is one of the oldest civilizations in the world. Historically, Universities and libraries were a big part of the Indus Valley Civilization. The two famous ancient universities of India and the oldest universities in the world are *Takshashila (Taxila)* and Nalanda. Nalanda was established in the fifth century AD in Bihar, India, and survived until circa 1200 AD. It was devoted to Buddhist studies and trained students in fine arts, medicine, mathematics, astronomy, politics, and the art of war. Ancient *Taxila*, or *Takshashila*, in ancient *Gandhara*, was an early Hindu and Buddhist learning center. Today, India is attracting students from Afghanistan, Africa, China, Japan, Maldives, Canada, France, Iran, Iraq, Germany, Australia, the UK, the USA, and other nations. This unbelievable educational progress also includes lower tuition costs compared to western countries. The country has also made remarkable progress in the field of medical research, software engineers providing skilled doctors and engineers to most of Europe at a minimal salary. The world owes ancient India for the gift of one of the significant contributions of Vedic civilizations. India is blessed to have given the world the gift of Buddha, whose divine fragrance of Buddhism and cultural heritage spread from India to all corners of the globe. This is the wisdom of this magnificent land and a great nation. Great personalities like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Swami Vivekananda, and Mahatma Gandhi have also left their footsteps in the country, which has a glorious tradition of pluralism and respect for diversity and beliefs. In Indian culture, art, languages, literature, festivals, and practices, we see the indelible mark of timeless Buddhist preaching and the philosophy of non-violence espoused by Mahatma Gandhi.

2.0 THE TRUE IMAGE OF INDIAN REALITY

There comes a part of the essay where the ultimate objective remains what is achieved by dedicated thoughts written in black & white, like once; a wise man said: “if a man is worth his salt, he must prove that his pen is mightier than his sword”. The international effects of Indian education and culture are time immemorial and trace back to antiquity. It has more feasible to understand what soft-power means, a term coined by Harvard academic Joseph Knight quotes, “the ability to attract or gravitate nations towards it because of its cultural, political values. a policy crafted by minds through toils of education and learning its partly

due to the never-ending efforts of the government. The tedious transformation of education is the new face of open diplomacy and the art of foreign policy to influence others. What is vital in this information era, it is not the nation with a superior army or that possesses true power; India has come a long way from being a land of sages & Sadhus to a strategic landmark of mathematical geniuses and tech wizards; you would love to hear the story how it all got started, since India has 75% of the potential human resources being the nuts & bolts of the most considerable Research & Development melting pots in the world NASA & Google we have an Indian CEO Sathya Nadella, etc. Indians usually are understood as physically poor but psychologically rich. The story rests on the common platform of democratic & political pluralism. India was a refuge for the Jews since the destruction of Babylonian temples. To the Tibetans under the leadership of Dalai Lama, Indian Dharamshala is a sanctuary against the hostile Chinese occupation. When the war is against love and freedom of life, India stood as a beacon of peace for all the lost ones on stormy waters or stony shores and a natural destination for the most refuged neighbors. With the most significant voting populace & the largest democratic franchise in the entire human history on the face of the earth, India stands as a model to its neighboring states to pursue a complex path of the legal and democratic way of life, the choice of making right is often the hardest one. The great success story of India is in a country where so many learned wise men valued their lives in the pursuit of knowledge. If there is anything worth celebrating about India, it is not the military muscle or economic power. However, all is necessary; there is more to it than overcoming the pestilence of poverty and national concerns. Generational wealth is in its store of knowledge; its ideals not materialistic but venture into the ability to innovate and multiply in vast directions on its quest for wisdom. The challenges it has overcome in a rich & diverse society, determined to liberate & fulfill, proliferate the creative energies of all the nations that seek its favor. India is the fastest-growing economy in the world. By 2030, India will become the third largest economy, surpassing China and the USA, with projected GDP of \$30 Trillion. Our land boasts of having close to one lakh fifty-five thousand six hundred post offices across the country, which is the largest postal network in the world. Besides, India is the 19th largest exporter and the 10th largest importer in the world.

The recent highlight is India's first successful Mars Orbiter Mission - Mangalyaan completed a 400-million km journey to Mars, becoming the first Asian country and fourth in the world to undertake a mission to the red planet. With all these successes, what is our hope for the

future? In days to come, we hope and look forward that India will be accorded permanent membership in the UN Security Council through which peace can be ensured in the region.

3.0 INDIAN COUNCIL FOR CULTURAL RELATIONS (ICCR)

It is also a good time to recall its founder. Maulana Abul Kalam Azad was a key figure in the Indian independence movement. He was a brilliant scholar and poet as well. During his time as Minister, various initiatives were established to boost primary and secondary education, scientific education, university establishment, and research and higher education opportunities. He founded several institutions, including the *Sahitya Akademi*, the Sangeet Natak Akademi, the Lalit Kala Akademi, and the Indian Council for Cultural Relations. He provided a significant impetus for establishing higher education institutions, such as the prestigious Indian Institutes of Technology. Maulana Abul Kalam Azad received India's highest civilian award, the Bharat Ratna, in 1992 for his outstanding contribution to the country.⁵ Maulana Abul Kalam Azad, a prominent independence fighter and independent India's first Education Minister, established the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) on April 9th, 1950. Its goals are;

- (a). to actively participate in formulating strategies and training programs;*
- (b). to foster and strengthen cultural relations and mutual*
- (c). to promote cultural exchanges with other countries and people, and*
- (d). to develop relationships with nations.*

Likewise, every state and culture are woven together by a complicated tapestry of individual values, conventions, and history; thus, understanding their culture is to comprehend them. The world's most considerable beauty stems from its diversity of people. Cultural linkages provide the foundation of people-to-people relationships, establishing an ecosystem of long-term peace and harmony. By hosting countless cultural events worldwide and exchanging artists and intellectuals through various scholarships and fellowships, the ICCR has played a significant role in connecting people and spreading Indian culture.

The Council pursues its cultural diplomacy role through a range of initiatives. In addition to organizing cultural festivals in India and overseas, ICCR conducts a wide range of cultural, academic, and intellectual activities in the realm of Indian culture, including Indian dance, music, yoga, languages, cuisines, various festivals, essay writing competitions, ethos, and customs, as well as contemporary concerns, through its Indian Cultural Centres. ICCR has spent decades effectively using its resources to promote an image of India that enhances India's inherent historical attractiveness while also bolstering cultural diplomacy and foreign

policy. To foster mutual understanding and maintain peaceful relations, the Constitution of India stipulates in Article 51. The State shall endeavour to —

- (a) Promote international peace and security;*
- (b) Maintain just and honorable relations between nations;*
- (c) Foster respect for international law and*
- (d) Encourage settlement of international disputes by arbitration.*

Major programs carried out under the auspices of the ICCR with the overarching goal of promoting a better knowledge of Indian culture within the global community may be generally classified as follows:

- i. Sponsoring visits of Indian cultural delegations abroad and holding India Festivals internationally;*
- ii. Hosting foreign cultural troupes and international Cultural Festivals in India;*
- iii. Art and Craft Exhibitions in India and abroad; IV. Gifting Busts and Statues of India's Iconic Figures Oversea;*
- iv. Promotion of Yoga and celebration of International Day of Yoga abroad;*
- v. Conducting Annual Lecture Series (Deen Dayal Upadhaya Memorial Oration to mark World Culture Day on May 21) and*
- vi. Promotion of Indian languages, notably Hindi and Sanskrit, as well as Indian literature, overseas;*

ICCR is working to its fullest extent to facilitate and improve foreign relations regarding education. Currently, the following schemes are available:

General Scholarship Scheme – ICCR - The GSS is one of the important scholarship schemes of ICCR for Foreign Students, which is awarded at the level of undergraduate/postgraduate levels and for pursuing research to foreign students from Asian and Latin American Countries. Apart from this, initiatives for the following specific categories have been taken up by the ICCR Bangladesh Scholarship Scheme – ICCR, Commonwealth Scholarship Scheme – ICCR, Nehru Memorial Scholarship Scheme – ICCR, CEP/EEP Scholarship Scheme – ICCR.

The government of India, under the Ministry of External Affairs, has the following policies under its banner:

Silver Jubilee Scholarship Scheme – MEA, AYUSH Scholarship Scheme for BIMSTEC Countries – MEA, Aid-to-Maldives Scholarship Scheme – MEA, Mekong Ganga Co-operation Scholarship Scheme – MEA, Afghan Scholarship Scheme – MEA, Africa

Scholarship Scheme – MEA, Aid-to-Mongolia Scholarship Scheme – MEA, Nehru Memorial Scholarship Scheme – MEA, Maulana Azad Scholarship Scheme – MEA, Rajiv Gandhi Scholarship Scheme – MEA, India Scholarship (Bangladesh) Scheme – MEA, Aid-to-Bhutan Scholarship Scheme – MEA, AYUSH Scholarship Scheme for Non-BIMSTEC Countries, AYUSH Scholarship Scheme for Malaysian Nationals, AYUSH Scholarship Scheme for South East Asian Region (SEAR) Countries, Scholarship Scheme for Children/Dependents of Afghan Nationals Defence & Security Forces – MEA, Scholarship to Wards of Border Guard Bangladesh – MEA.

This is a great way to showcase India's enduring and vibrant culture and incredible diversity. Major Festivals where ICCR participates include the Cervantino Festival, Janadriyah – the annual National Heritage and Cultural Festival, Golden Jubilee of Indo-Bhutan Diplomatic Relations, and Celebrations of 70 Years of India-Nepal Diplomatic Ties. ICCR proposes to sponsor many cultural groups in the coming months for participation in some important events like “Glimpses of India Festival” (Egypt), “SEA Festival” (Cambodia), “Tiranga Festival” (Senegal) on the occasion of Republic Day & Holi Utsav celebrations.

Additionally, over time the ICCR has positioned itself as the most visible face of India's global cultural involvement. One such edge is the Little Guru App, Little Guru App, an online instructor of the old Indian language Sanskrit. Learning Sanskrit is unquestionably a gateway to understanding Indian culture and traditions. The app teaches many levels of Sanskrit, ranging from alphabets to speaking, reading, and writing text, allowing users to go from basic to advanced Sanskrit. Sanskrit, while also an essential modern language mentioned in the 8th Schedule of the Constitution of India, possesses classical literature that is greater in volume than that of Latin and Greek put together, containing vast treasures of mathematics, philosophy, grammar, music, politics, medicine, architecture, metallurgy, drama, poetry, storytelling, and more (known as Sanskrit Knowledge Systems'), written by people of various religions as well as non-religious people, and by people from all walks of life and a wide range of socio-economic backgrounds over thousands of years. Sanskrit exists indefinitely it has no beginning and no end. It will continue forever. It was initially employed in the Vedas and has since become a form of expression in various professions. Valmiki created the Adikavya Ramayana in Sanskrit, with seven sections and 24000 couplets filled with the most powerful imagery, idioms, metaphors, wisdom, and dignity. In truth, the contributions to the richness of Sanskrit literature did not originate from just one area or state

in India; they came from throughout the country. Other classical languages in India, such as classical Tamil, Telugu, Kannada, Malayalam, and Odia, have vibrant literature. In addition to these classical languages, the works of literature written in Pali, Persian, and Prakrit must be preserved for posterity's enjoyment and education. As India develops, the next generation will wish to engage with and be enriched by the country's vast and exquisite classical literature. The Constitutional provisions relating to the Eighth Schedule occur in articles 344(1) and 351 of the Constitution. The official languages of India are listed in the Eighth Schedule to the Indian Constitution. Even though there are hundreds of languages spoken throughout the country, the eighth schedule recognizes them as official languages. While of these languages were initially listed in the constitution, the remaining languages were added through subsequent changes. Today, you can see an Indian relationship in any region of the earth. I ascribe it to the following factors:

4.0 SOFT POWER

The term "Soft power" was first coined by Nye in 1990 in his book "Bound to Lead: The Changing Nature of American Power." Since then, the significance of this concept has increased dramatically, and many scholars of international politics have been taking a keen interest in it. According to Nye, a country may obtain the outcomes it wants in world politics because other countries admire its values, emulate its example, aspire to its level of prosperity and openness, and wish to follow it. In this sense, it is imperative to set the agenda and attract others in world politics and only to force them to change by threatening military force or economic sanctions. Soft power rests on the ability to shape the preference of others. The evolution of soft power in international politics has implications for developing countries and India in particular. It has a direct effect on India's foreign policy choices and alternatives. It means acknowledging that India's claims to a significant leadership role in the world of the twenty-first century relate to aspects and products of Indian Society and Culture that the world finds attractive.

These assets may not directly persuade others to support India, but they go a long way toward enhancing India's intangible standing in the world's eye. Regarding soft power, India's position is significantly high in some areas while it has considerable potential in others. India could always count itself among the few nations with solid cards in the arena of soft power", asserting that India's most prominent "instrument" of soft power was its diaspora. Indian diaspora is undeniably an asset. Beyond its cultural and civilizational riches, it's vibrant (if at times chaotic) democracy, its free media, its mostly independent judiciary, its dynamic civil

society, and the unique struggle for human rights since independence all make it attractive to people in much of the world where these characteristics of its national experience are known. In addition, India's largely nonviolent defeat of colonialism served as an essential beacon for freedom movements and newly independent countries elsewhere in the 1950s and 1960s.

Strength of

4.1 Diversity India,

the fabled land of seers, sages, spiritual leaders, and healers has been a beacon of light for the West for centuries. It is known for its tremendous cultural power that has profoundly impacted the world for thousands of years. The richness of India's culture manifests in diverse traditions, languages, faiths, and rituals that lend wealth and depth. Today, Indian spirituality is attracting people from all over the world. Every diverse culture in India and other parts of the world flourishes, Hence, ICCR's existence is a matter of pride and joy. ICCR is contributing immensely to strengthening the connection between India and other countries.

4.2 Vibrant Indian Diaspora

The thriving Indian Diaspora is actively contributing to the promotion of Indian culture. India now has a diaspora of over 30 million people living in other countries. For instance, Nobel Laureates, Booker Prize winners, Emmy Awardees, eminent physicians, engineers, businessmen, IT specialists, artists, and spiritual leaders are all represented Indian culture. Wherever they go, the diaspora has produced successful businesspeople, well-loved educators, astronauts, celebrities in every field, and civic-minded citizens. For Instance, India has 75% of the potential human resources being the nuts & bolts of the most prominent Research & Development melting pots in the world, NASA & Google CEO, India Sathya Nadella, etc. Indian music and dance in Bollywood are not only practiced by Indians only now, but it has also traveled abroad. The countries like Turkey, Russia, and Gulf nations, have separate channels to telecast Indian movies and Dramas, though in the dubbed format. Bollywood, the soft power of India, has not only helped the Indian Diaspora stay connected to its culture, but the people of the host country have also developed their interest in the Indian culture. Some countries even celebrate the festivals of India like Diwali and Holi.

4.3 Yoga

Yoga is a way to learn and understand spiritual India. Also, yoga is associated with the culture and heritage of India. In Sanskrit, yoga means 'unite' and describes a healthy way to

live. Many people from India and foreigners resort to yoga and meditation to de-stress and rejuvenate their minds. Yoga is an invaluable gift of India's ancient tradition. It embodies unity of mind and body; thought and action; restraint and fulfillment, harmony between man and nature; a holistic approach to health and well-being. It is not about exercise but discovering a sense of oneness with yourself, the world, and personality. Yoga and Ayurveda have become the symbols of India outside India. India is a nation of unity in diversity.

4.4 The doctrine of Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam

Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam has become a catch-all notion for India's diplomatic orthodoxy to be deployed in numerous scenarios. Although it might be open to myriad interpretations, it has been used to broadly convey India's ideal and liberal concept of global norms, themes of globalization, or global commons. Doing so suggests that this is a perfect world worth achieving and can be created through negotiations alone. India is taking practical steps to spread this concept of Unity through Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam. From Jawaharlal Nehru to Narendra Modi, Indian leaders have often evoked the phrase Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam (the world is one family), taken from the Maha Upanishad, to elucidate the country's global outlook. While the term has become a mantra of India's diplomatic lexicon.

4.5 Non-violence

One of the most famous leaders of a non-violent movement was Mohandas K. Gandhi (1869-1948), who opposed British imperial rule in India during the 20th century.²¹ Gandhi took the religious principle of ahimsa (not harm) common to Buddhism, Hinduism, and Jainism and turned it into a non-violent tool for mass action. He used it to fight not only colonial rule but also social evils such as racial discrimination and untouchability. Gandhi called it "*satyagraha*," which means 'truth force.' In this doctrine, non-violent conflict aims to convert the opponent, win over his mind and heart, and persuade him to your point of view. Gandhi was firm that satyagraha was not a weapon of the weak - "Satyagraha is a weapon of the strong; it admits of no violence under any circumstance whatever, and it always insists upon truth." Among the non-violent protest, techniques are Peaceful demonstrations, sit-ins, picketing, holding vigils, fasting, hunger strikes, strike blockades, and civil disobedience. According to M.K Gandhi, nonviolence is a power that can be wielded equally by all - children, young men, and women or grown-up people, provided they have a living faith in the God of Love and have, therefore, equal love for all mankind. When non-violence is accepted as the law of life, it must pervade the whole being and not be applied to isolated acts. Non-violence is an active force of the highest order. It is the soul force or the power of Godhead

within us. In 3000 years of Indian history, people from all different parts of the world have come and invaded India, Yet India has not done this to any other nation. Why? Because Indians respect others' freedom.

5.0 UNIVERSITY OF MYSORE

The University of Mysore is frequently the top choice for higher study in India among foreign students. International students at the institution come from about 60 different countries. The University of Mysore collaborates with the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR), diplomatic missions, universities, and research organizations from various countries to assist student and scholar admissions.

6.0 MYSORE CITY

Mysuru, is a significant cultural centre in India, is noted for its multicultural environment and is a great destination for international students to pursue their academic interests as well as their passions for the arts, sports, and Yoga.

7.0 INDIA AND AFGHANISTAN

We are proud to stand with each other and walk together. The friendship between India and Afghanistan was etched in time by the "Great Master," i.e., *Mahatma Gandhi and Khan Ghafar Khan (Frontier Gandhi)*. They imparted an ever-present radiance to our relationship. As close neighbors, our relationship spreads across many layers. Ours is a friendship that lives in the hearts of our people and the fabric of our societies. We believe that the free flow of trade, investments, technology, and ideas across our borders will be to our mutual benefit. India's rapid growth can bring dividends for the entire region, especially in Afghanistan. Indians contribute not to compete but to lay the foundations of a brighter future, not to light the flame of conflict or to destroy a nation, but to rebuild lives and breathe meaning into them. Our development partnership stretches across nearly every sector of human activity, such as agriculture, education, health, resettlement, transport, power, culture, water, shelter, sports, and human resources. Our ties are as ancient as history. In the heart of every Indian and Afghan, there is boundless love for each other. We love each other's culture and cinema, music and poetry, food and festivals. And, now, we admire each other's cricket.

8.0 INDIA AS MY EDUCATION DESTINY

I am thrilled to have this opportunity to be a student at the University of Mysore. According to Maulana Abul Kalam Azad, "*Educationists should build the capacities of the spirit of inquiry, creativity, entrepreneurial and moral leadership among students and become their*

role model.” Education excellence is a significant milestone of intellectual growth and is the beginning of a life journey. I come from a land where history has been shared with India for a thousand years but still has a distinct identity and image of its own; more so ever, my country is red with the bloodshed of its natives, the land so fertile for any life to grow but the seeds of war are deeply sown that would take decades to eradicate the malice and hatred against the insurgencies and the civil war. Although there is an existing belief that there cannot be everlasting peace built on the ruins of war, as summed in the Latin maxim " *Si Vis Pacem, Parabellum,*" which means “if you wish for peace, then one must prepare for war”; there is some truth to that statement. I was born into an Afghan family that had to witness first-hand tumults of civil war and conflicts. Sadly, this has become a relic of the past, shadowed in the annals of our history. I consider myself to be enormously fortunate to reap the fruits of an education in a land of pioneering geniuses and masters of the age of Indian enlightenment, such as *Aryabhata* for his invention of zero, without which the number system is a fallacy, *Shusrutha* in the field of medicine, etc. I seized the day with the stellar success for straight these years that is owed to this great country India and thousands of others like me who paved their roads to skills development, the privilege this country has bestowed upon me, a debt that a word of gratitude cannot surmount. Still, if this is my article, it shall stand as a testimony to the cultural and diplomatic relationships the union of two great nations was laid upon the foundation stones of education and literacy. Ability is nothing without opportunity, so we are defined by the moments we seize. My recipe for success was not a “*Cinderella Story,*” I’ve been under the sky some cold nights, the puzzled moon as a witness, having seen some kids struggle and bury a few of my comrades. Seeing all these years of hardship has disciplined my mindset. I never looked for motivation, nor can I boast about the imaginative ways of my conscience. But one must try to commit mistakes to learn from them, for the talent I possess is the contribution of the tolerant Indian teachers who were steadfast in allowing my comedy of errors so that I could listen and learn. In all these years, my true Indian friends, through their rich culture, helped me to understand freedom of life and the legacy of respecting others. In partaking in this rich legacy of non-violence, constructed my state of mind with monumental architecture, every step towards the improvisation of my mind is a milestone to truly justify that the purpose of education is not to fill a container but to ignite the senses of free-thinkers, the choice I made to study in India saved me from drowning in my one-dimensional conservative mindset to a progressive, democratic and broad way of life where freedom of religion is respected. I am proud to say that I have made

the righteous use of this invaluable chance to acknowledge the gift of giving; this is unquestionably an act of auspicious enfranchisement; it certainly ranks among the lines the *Full-bright* (USA), *Chevening* (UK), and *DAAD* (Germany) Scholarships acumen. I am rendering a bid to the institution with a lot of memories that are unforgettable in my mind, with the courage to face the challenges ahead and also with enthusiastic perseverance. Last but not the least, Indians are immensely kind, generous, and mindful of others at every point of need. We are genuinely privileged to be here in India, a country of great freedom of life and religion.

9.0 EPILOGUE

India has promoted a soft power approach through a series of new initiatives framed around concepts of 'non-reciprocity', 'connectivity' and 'asymmetrical responsibilities', which indicate a willingness to use economic attractiveness to persuade its neighbours rather than coercive military capacities. Since 1980 it has resulted in a greater political investment in different regional institutions such as the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC), the South Asia Cooperative Environment Programme, the South Asian Economic Union and BIMSTEC which were created to enhance cultural and commercial ties. Thus, India seeks a peaceful periphery and works for good neighbourly relations in her extended neighborhood. India's foreign policy also recognizes that issues such as climate change, energy and food security are crucial for India's transformation. Since these issues are global in nature, they require global solutions.

SAYED QUDRAT HASHIMY
(ICCR, ALUMNI, AFGHANISTAN)